

Prosthetic Management of Missing Anterior teeth with Maryland Bridge as a Minimally Invasive treatment Modality

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Submitted 16 April 2025
Accepted 29 October 2025
Published xx xxx xxxx

Access this Article Online
Website: www.healtalk.in
DOI
Quick Response Code

Abstract

An anterior tooth loss presents a functional, aesthetic, and rehabilitation challenge, particularly for individuals in the younger age range. For these patients, a minimally invasive option for function and aesthetic restoration is a resin bonded fixed partial denture. A kind of resin bonded bridge called a Maryland bridge includes supragingival borders, which prevent pulp stress and preserve periodontal health. The Maryland bridge is described in this case study as a successful treatment option for replacing lost anterior teeth.

Keywords: Maryland bridge, minimally invasive, restoration.

Introduction

Young patients experience significant psychological effects in addition to functional loss when their anterior teeth are lost. The replacement of the lost maxillary lateral incisor is crucial because the empty space in the maxillary anterior region affects the patient's mental health, particularly if they are a young patient. There are a number of treatment options available for replacing lost maxillary incisors, including fixed partial dentures, removable partial dentures, and implants. Because it may result in bone resorption and the flattening of the interdental papillae with prolonged use, a removable partial denture can be utilized as an interim prosthesis for initial esthetics. In order to replace the missing tooth and preserve the remaining alveolar ridge and soft tissue, a more conservative and less invasive resin bonded prosthesis may be an alternative treatment for conditions like these because of the large pulp chambers and lack of sufficient enamel.^{2,3} Implants are a superior treatment option, but where they are placed depends on a number of variables, such as the patient's preferences, the quantity of available bone, and a number of medical and financial considerations.¹

In this case study, the maryland bridge is used as a successful, minimally invasive treatment option to replace the missing maxillary anterior lateral incisor.⁴

Case Report

A 36 year old female patient visited the Department of Prosthodontics with concerns about the unesthetic appearance caused by the loss of her upper anterior teeth. She repor-

ted a history of tooth extraction following trauma to the upper anterior region, which had occurred six months prior. Upon intraoral examination, the right lateral incisor was found to be missing, accompanied by a slight rotation of the right canine.(Figure 1A).

Fig. 1a and 1b: Intraoral mandibular view showing missing left central incisor

A concavity was present labially in the region of the missing central incisor. All the treatment options including implant, conventional fixed dental prosthesis, removable partial denture, and resin bonded bridges were given to the patient. The patient was not willing for any invasive treatment option, so implants were opted out. She was willing for fixed prosthesis with minimal tooth reduction, so resin bonded bridges were chosen as the treatment option for the patient.

Technique

Both the maxillary and mandibular arch diagnostic impressions were made. Diagnostic casts were obtained and the wax up for the missing tooth was done. Tooth preparation was done on the lingual surfaces of the right

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central incisor and right canine (13 and 11) with a chamfer finish line prepared supra-gingivally.

The incisal end of the tooth preparation was kept 1 mm cervical from the incisal edge (Figure 2).

Fig. 2: Tooth preparation on the lingual surface of 11 and 13 teeth.

Fig. 3: Final impression of the mandibular arch using double step putty wash impression technique.

Gingiva was retracted using the retraction cord and the final impression was made using the two step putty wash impression technique using additional silicone impression material (Figure 3). Indirect temporization was done and the provisional restoration was luted using temporary non eugenol based cement (Figure 4).

Fig. 4: Frontal view of temporization of the left lateral incisor

Fig. 5: A) Intraoral frontal view showing the maryland bridge cemented to the adjacent teeth, B) Intraoral mandibular view showing the lingual surface of the final prosthesis.

The nickel chromium metal framework was fabricated and try in was done, followed by ceramic build up on the lateral incisor. The prosthesis was finished, polished and glazed. The final prosthesis was luted using the self-etch resin cement (Rely X U200,3M ESPE, Germany) on the abutment teeth (Figure 5). The occlusion was assessed and post cementation instructions were given to the patient. Patient was kept on follow-up at regular intervals and she was satisfied with the result.

Discussion

Pulp chambers in fixed partial dentures are so large, hence tooth preparation of all abutment teeth surfaces is necessary for the restoration of missing teeth. In younger patients, this can result in pulp damage. In such a situation, resin bonded fixed dental prostheses are a useful option. The University of Maryland developed the "Maryland Bridge," a fixed dental prosthesis that is bonded with resin. The retention of the resin bonded prosthesis has improved due to the development of new resin cements that chemically bond to the etched metal alloy as well as the tooth surface^{3,5}. Micromechanical retention is utilized to maintain the integrity of the Maryland Bridge. Only non-precious alloys can be used with the alloy-specific Maryland bridges because precious alloys cannot be etched to provide the micromechanical retention.

A Maryland bridge has a number of benefits, such as less tooth preparation to preserve the enamel, less pulpal trauma, a lower risk of causing gingival irritation, a single path of insertion to prevent displacement, improved aesthetics, patient satisfaction, and the avoidance of the need for local anesthetic^{6,7}. But it also has some drawbacks, such as the technique-sensitive application and the metal retainer's propensity to show through the thin anterior teeth.^{8,9}

A few things to think about when choosing a case are para-functional habits, periodontal diseases, adequate occlusal clearance, no severe rotation or malpositioning of the abutment teeth, and adequate thickness of enamel. A few things to think about when choosing a case are parafunctional habits, periodontal diseases, adequate occlusal clearance, no severe rotation or malpositioning of the abutment teeth, and adequate thickness of enamel.

Conclusion

A successful method of replacing lost teeth, restoring function and aesthetics, and enhancing patient confidence is with resin bonded bridges. When it comes to small span restorations, resin bonded bridges ought to be given more consideration. This is especially true when careful patient evaluation and prudent clinical techniques are employed.

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